

Research Article

Failure mechanisms in quenching and partitioning (Q&P) steel under varying stress states

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history:

Received 5 May 2025

Revised 7 September 2025

Accepted 8 September 2025

Available online 20 September 2025

Keywords:

Fracture mechanisms

Multiphase steel

Stress triaxiality

Cleavage fracture

Phase segmentation

Q&P 1000 steel

ABSTRACT

Quenching and partitioning (Q&P) steels represent a key advancement in third-generation advanced high-strength steels (AHSS), offering an exceptional balance between strength and ductility due to their complex multiphase microstructures. However, their application in crash-critical and formability-sensitive components remains limited by an incomplete understanding of their fracture behavior under complex stress states. Therefore, this study aims to systematically investigate the failure mechanisms of Q&P 1000 steel across a wide range of stress states from shear to uniaxial and plane-strain tension using tensile specimens with different geometries. By combining macroscopic mechanical testing with detailed microstructural characterization via scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD), we reveal a transition from ductile fracture, governed by void nucleation and coalescence, to cleavage-dominated fracture under increasing triaxiality. Remarkably, transgranular cleavage fracture features were observed for the first time in Q&P steels even after substantial plastic deformation, which confirms it to be also a failure mechanism of ductile fracture in addition to brittle fracture. Two major damage mechanisms responsible for the failure mode transition were revealed: (i) phase boundary debonding and (ii) martensite cleavage fracture. A stress-based cleavage fracture criterion with a critical stress triaxiality, regulated by the cleavage fracture stress and strain hardening behavior, can well explain and quantify this transition behavior. These results provide new insights into stress-state-dependent failure in Q&P steels and offer guidance for their safe and optimized application in forming and crash-relevant components.

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1. Introduction

Advanced high-strength steels (AHSS) are key materials for meeting both the consumption and safety requirements of modern vehicles, driven by the push for lightweight design and energy conservation [1,2]. Previous research [3,4] has introduced the quenching and partitioning (Q&P) process of the third-generation AHSS. Q&P steel undergoes a specific heat treatment process that might form martensite, ferrite, bainite, as well as retained austenite. The mechanical interaction of martensite/austenite (M/A) and the formation of mechanically induced martensite through the transformation-induced plasticity (TRIP) effect [5–7] ensures a harmonious balance between strength and ductility. Researchers have been particularly interested in this material because of its remarkable balance of these features [8–10]. Compared to the first-

generation dual-phase (DP) steel, Wang and Speer [11] demonstrated that Q&P 980 steel exhibited superior ductility, reaching a level comparable to that of DP780. These advantages make it a preferred material for applications requiring lightweight, durable components. However, strength and ductility alone are insufficient to assess the full performance of AHSS. Increasing attention has turned to local formability, damage tolerance, and fracture behavior under complex stress states, which are crucial for predicting performance in real-world forming and crash scenarios.

Casellas et al. [12] and Hiser et al. [13] demonstrated that it is important to assess not only tensile properties but also hole expansion and bending performance, as these tests provide valuable insight into local formability. The overall behavior of Q&P steels under external loading is not always satisfactory; in particular, they display an obvious weakness when the loading conditions are complex. Li et al. [14] compared the hole-expansion ratio of two AHSS, including DP1000 and Q&P 1000. They reported that Q&P steel has much lower local formability in terms of hole expansion ra-

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tio, while its global formability (ductility) is more than twice that of DP1000. In addition, Li et al. [15] also reported that the local formability of Q&P 1000 is very sensitive to stress states, especially for loading along the transverse direction. This strong sensitivity means that damage and fracture in Q&P parts can vary widely with the way a component is formed, such as bent, sheared, or stretched. Therefore, understanding how Q&P steel fails under different stress states is essential for safe and reliable application in automotive structures.

A large body of research [16–19] demonstrates that metallic materials typically fail by ductile fracture at room temperature, dominantly controlled by void nucleation, growth, and coalescence. Voids nucleate around inclusions, second-phase particles, or highly strained slip bands [20–22]. As plastic deformation continues, these voids grow and eventually link as the remaining ligaments' neck and tear. It further results in void coalescence and produces a characteristic dimpled fracture surface. This framework gives a benchmark for evaluating the failure behavior of most metals and alloys. Similarly, several studies intended to reveal the failure mechanism of the Q&P steels. Kang et al. [23] classified four types of strain localization incidents based on the neighborhood microstructure of Q&P 1000 steel, and they all contribute to the ductile failure mechanism. Meanwhile, Cheng et al. [24] employed crystal plasticity finite element modeling to further mimic the qualitative ductile failure mechanisms of Q&P steels. However, recent findings challenge the universality of this void-dominated model in Q&P steels. Xiong et al. [5] observed mixed-mode fracture surfaces for two types of sample geometries (normal tensile sample and sharp-notched dog-bone sample), combining ductile dimples with intergranular facets. Shen et al. [25] further reported that purely intergranular fractures occurred even after substantial macroscopic plastic deformation. These observations indicate that Q&P steels, despite their high ductility, may experience a fracture mode transition from ductile to brittle failure under specific conditions, particularly at high stress triaxialities.

Such a transition is surprising, as intergranular fracture is classically associated with brittle behavior and low ductility. The coexistence of intergranular fracture features with large strains challenges the traditional assumption that extensive plastic deformation rules out brittle mechanisms. Moreover, the underlying microstructural causes, including the transformation of retained austenite into martensite, the presence of M/A islands along grain boundaries, the brittleness of the fresh and tempered martensite, etc., remain underexplored. While previous studies suggest that stress triaxiality is a key factor in driving this transition [5], a systematic and comprehensive investigation quantifying the critical triaxiality at which the fracture mode switches has not yet been conducted. Furthermore, the underlying micromechanical and microstructural origins of this transition are still not clearly understood.

Addressing this knowledge gap is challenging due to the intrinsic microstructural complexity of Q&P steels. Retained austenite undergoes dynamic transformation under strain, altering local phase morphology and mechanical response in real-time [26,27]. In addition, differentiating all the body-centered cubic (BCC) phases (ferrite, tempered martensite, fresh martensite, and even bainite) is inherently difficult. These complexities of Q&P steels are increased by microstructural heterogeneity, as slight variations in manufacturing processes can lead to significant differences in microstructural compositions [3,28–31]. Consequently, the link between macroscopic failure behavior and micromechanical mechanisms remains insufficiently resolved.

To fill the current knowledge gap, this study, therefore, aims to perform a systematic experimental investigation revealing the failure mechanisms in Q&P 1000 steel under a wide range of stress states. The key objectives are: (1) to examine how stress

Table 1
Chemical composition of the Q&P 1000 steel (wt%).

C	Si	Mn	Al	Cr	Co	Mo+Ni+Cu	P+S+Nb
0.15	1.67	2.42	0.074	0.02	0.026	< 0.01	< 0.006

states affect the fracture mechanism, with an emphasis on the transition from ductile to “brittle” fracture governing mechanisms, (2) to identify the microstructural features (e.g., phase boundaries, austenite morphology, martensitic features) that act as initiation sites for voids and cracks under different loading conditions; and (3) to derive a mechanics-based understanding of the failure mechanism transition for the new high-strength steels. Accordingly, tensile experiments were designed using a set of specimens with tailored geometries, such as smooth dog-bone (SDB), notched dog-bone (NDB), central-hole (CH), and shear (SH), to achieve a broad spectrum of stress states. Post-fracture analysis employed high-resolution scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and electron backscatter diffraction (EBSD) to investigate the microstructural origin of fracture across different regimes. By combining stress-state control, detailed microstructural analysis, and advanced characterization techniques, the study offers a novel contribution by linking stress-state-dependent failure modes with micromechanical mechanisms, which challenges the prevailing assumption that ductility precludes cleavage fracture. The findings will have direct implications for the design, processing, and application of Q&P steels in forming and crash-critical components.

In the following, the study introduces the experiment design and material characterization methods of fractured specimens. Section 3 presents a phase segmentation method based on EBSD and the MTEX toolbox for Q&P 1000, as well as the fracture morphology and failure mechanism under different stress states with various stress triaxialities. In Section 4, we discuss how microstructure, stress state, and other factors influence the damage and fracture behavior of Q&P 1000 steel.

2. Material and experiments

2.1. Material selection

The 3rd advanced high-strength automotive Q&P steel (Q&P 1000) with a thickness of about 1.5 mm was selected as the investigated material in this study. The chemical composition measured via a BELEC LAB 3000s optical emission spectrometer is given in Table 1. The microstructure of the Q&P steel is complex and is influenced by various factors such as quenching temperature (T_Q), quenching time (t_Q), partitioning temperature (T_P), and partitioning time (t_P). These different combinations of temperature and time pairings often result in widely varying microstructures of Q&P steels [32–34].

2.2. Mechanical testing

To characterize the plastic behavior, with a particular focus on the initiation stage of damage of Q&P 1000 during the entire loading process, uniaxial tensile tests along the rolling direction were conducted. The tests were carried out using a Zwick/Roell Z020 screw-driven tensile testing machine with a maximum load capacity of 20 kN. A constant crosshead velocity of 0.36 mm min⁻¹ was selected, corresponding to a quasi-static strain rate of 2×10^{-4} s⁻¹ prior to necking, given the specimen gauge length of 30 mm. As shown in Fig. 1(a), Q&P 1000 steel shows an excellent combination of strength and ductility, with an ultimate tensile strength (UTS) over 1000 MPa, while maintaining a total elongation (TE) over 24 %.

Fig. 1. Room-temperature mechanical properties of Q&P 1000 steel with designed geometries. (a) Engineering stress–strain curve of SDB geometry and (b) force–displacement curves of the other geometries.

Fig. 2. Experimental testing plan and crack initiation sites. (a) Specimen geometries designed to achieve different stress states at the crack initiation sites; (b) schematic illustration of fracture initiation sites for each geometry, and (c) the specimen geometries with dimensions.

At room temperature, the ductile fracture properties of Q&P 1000 were experimentally determined by loading various specimen geometries, as shown in Fig. 2. Appropriate specimen geometrical design of uniaxial tension loading SDB specimens allows the simplest tensile tests to realize different stress states [35–39]. Under monotonic loading, cracks typically initiate at the location having the largest plastic deformation, often identified as the crack initiation point due to the most damage. The specific geometric features were created to trigger a certain stress state at the crack initiation point to investigate the stress-state dependency of fracture

[15]. These geometries included an SH specimen, a CH specimen with a diameter of 6 mm, three NDB specimens with radii of 10 mm (NDB-R10), 6 mm (NDB-R6), and 2 mm (NDB-R2). As shown in Fig. 2(a), the stress states are often characterized by stress triaxiality (η) and the Lode angle parameter ($\bar{\theta}$) [20,35,40–42], and the designed samples achieve different stress states ranging from shear, uniaxial tensile, to plane strain tensile at the crack initiation point following a locally proportional loading history. The corresponding crack initiation points for each geometry are highlighted in Fig. 2(b) to assist in the interpretation of the fracture surface

Fig. 3. Illustration of the specimens used in this study and panoramic images of the specimens cut from the stretched samples and the evaluated locations.

analyses. The details about the specific procedures and determination of the stress states can be found in earlier studies [43,44]. Fig. 2(c) lists the dimensions for all geometries (units in mm), including the hole diameter in the CH specimen ($\varnothing 6$) and the notch-root radii for the NDB specimens (R10, R6, and R2). The corresponding force–displacement curves of all the samples are shown in Fig. 1(b).

2.3. Microstructure and damage mechanism characterization

To comprehensively understand the microstructure of Q&P 1000 steel and its influence on mechanical properties, a combined approach via SEM and EBSD was adopted. For SEM analysis, the samples were polished using a sequence of sandpapers, starting from 240 grit and finishing with 2400 grit, followed by a final polishing step using 0.25 μm alumina suspension to achieve a mirror-like finish. The samples were then etched using a 2 % Nital solution to reveal the microstructure. SEM observations were carried out using a Zeiss Ultra 55 FESEM microscope, operated at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV and a working distance of 10 mm. A similar polishing protocol was also applied for EBSD sample preparation, but with an additional ion beam polishing step in a JEOL Ion Beam Cryo Cross Section Polisher at 6 kV for 10 min to minimize surface stress and deformation. EBSD measurements were performed on a JEOL JIB-4700F equipped with an Oxford Instruments EBSD system. The system was operated at 20 kV with a step size of 0.05 μm . The phase fraction and crystallographic orientation of the material were determined from the EBSD data using MTEX, a MATLAB toolbox.

The same characterization method was applied to fractured specimens to investigate the failure mechanism under complex stress conditions. Specimens after fracture were subjected to both fracture surface morphology and corresponding cross-section damage mechanism analysis. Fig. 3 illustrates the SEM sample preparation process for all fractured specimens. For each geometry of the fractured specimen, two different samples were prepared for a comprehensive failure mechanism analysis. Sample 1 was cut along

the dashed line in Fig. 3. It was used for investigating the fracture mode and its characteristics by analyzing the fracture surface morphology. Meanwhile, sample 2 was cut along the cross-section and proceeded to be a metallography specimen, repeated grinding and polishing, and eventually etching, as highlighted in the yellow area. This sample was able to show the relationship between defects, microstructure, and fracture behavior. It is used to determine the microscopic failure mechanism under various complex stress states.

3. Results

3.1. Microstructure characterization

This section aims to develop a workflow to separate the phases in Q&P steels and essentially quantify the phase volume fraction of each phase. This has been a long-standing challenge, mainly due to the many BCC phases all mixed. The Q&P 1000 steel in the present study consists of five phases: ferrite (F), tempered martensite (TM), bainite (B), fresh martensite (FM), and retained austenite (RA). Fig. 4(a–d) presents SEM observations of the undeformed specimen microstructure acquired using SE2 and InLens detectors at magnifications of 10 and 20 k times. It provides general qualitative insight into the morphology and distribution of several phases. Ferrite appears as shallow depressions in the microstructure and is characterized by flat and homogeneous surfaces with small amounts of carbide. Bainite and tempered martensite are difficult to differentiate in SEM images, but can be distinguished based on their shape characteristics. Tempered martensite has plate-like shapes or big block shapes [45], while bainite has slatted shapes.

Further phase segmentation and quantitative analysis of the different phases were carried out by EBSD, and many structural parameters that control the properties of the material can be derived from EBSD data, e.g., crystal structure, grain size, crystallographic orientation, etc. [46–48]. To particularly separate the BCC phases in the Q&P steels, this study established a specific segmentation strategy. The general workflow of phase segmentation is shown

Fig. 4. SEM and EBSD characterization of Q&P 1000 steel: (a–d) SEM images at 10 and 20 KX times using SE2 and InLens detectors. (e) PQ map showing phase segmentation criteria; (f) new phase map with four phases, RA, FM, F, TMB; (g) reconstructed prior austenite grain (PAG) map; (h) GOS map highlighting local misorientation.

Table 2
Strategy for constituents' identification of Q&P 1000.

Constituents	Phase	PQ	GOS	Grain size
Retained austenite	FCC	–	–	Small
Ferrite	BCC	High	Low	Large
Fresh martensite	BCC	Low	High	Small
Tempered martensite	BCC	Medium/High	Medium	Large
Bainite	BCC	Medium	Medium	Medium/Large

in Fig. 4, and Table 2 summarizes the various EBSD features for all phases. The segmentation strategy encompasses the following steps:

- (1) Separation of RA: retained austenite can be simply segmented due to its face-centered cubic (FCC) crystal structure from the other BCC phases. This is the first step in the workflow, as shown in Fig. 5. Since RA has a distinct FCC structure, its identification is straightforward using the phase map obtained from EBSD.
- (2) Separation of FM: FM has a low pattern quality (PQ) due to its high density of dislocations and defects, as shown in Fig. 4(e). The PQ map obtained from EBSD can be used to distinguish between FM and other BCC constituents [49,50], as it reflects the quality of the diffraction pattern obtained during analysis.
- (3) Separation of ferrite from other BCC phases: Ferrite can be initially separated based on PQ values, as it has a significantly higher PQ compared to TM and bainite. However, some TM and bainite have high PQ as well, which makes the ferrite segmentation not accurate. Grain orientation spread

(GOS) maps can be further employed to refine the separation. The GOS map serves as a crucial tool for differentiating ferrite from TM and bainite, as it quantifies the degree of misorientation among points within a grain. Lower GOS values indicate a more uniform grain orientation, while higher values suggest more internal strain or deformation. TM and bainite show a relatively high level of misorientation due to the prevalence of dislocations and structural defects, leading to elevated GOS values.

- (4) Classification of TM and bainite: After segmenting ferrite, the remaining BCC constituents are classified as tempered martensite and bainite (TMB), as they share similar structural characteristics. Due to the special hierarchical structure of bainite, it is difficult to segment it independently. Therefore, in this study, bainite is assumed to be incorporated into TMB as a composite phase.

After the complete phase segmentation process, the phase distribution map in Fig. 4(f) illustrates the morphology of all phases, including retained austenite (RA, red), ferrite (F, purple), tempered martensite/bainite (TMB, sky blue), and fresh martensite (FM, yellow). The quantified volume fraction for four components is RA ~8.4 %, F ~35.4 %, FM ~4.6 %, and TMB ~51.6 %. It is observed that RA exists in two morphologies: blocky and film-like. The film-like RA is primarily found within the martensitic hierarchical structures. The prior austenite grain (PAG) map (Fig. 4(g)) reveals the reconstruction of original austenite grains based on retained austenite and martensitic structures, which indicates that most blocky RA is located at prior austenite grain boundaries. The GOS map in Fig. 4(h) provides information about the misorientation within grains. The color gradient in the GOS map represents varying de-

Fig. 5. Schematic diagram of the phase segmentation process for multiphase steels.

degrees of misorientation, where blue indicates low misorientation (less deformation), while yellow to red represents high misorientation (high deformation and internal strain). For example, ferrite has low GOS values, confirming its nearly defect-free structure. TMB has moderate GOS values, reflecting internal strain. This further supports the phase segmentation strategy outlined in Fig. 5, which states that the GOS distribution is essential for distinguishing ferrite from TMB.

3.2. Fractography analysis of failure under various stress states

To reveal the initiation and progression of fracture in Q&P 1000 steel, a multiscale analysis of fracture surfaces was conducted across specimens subjected to various stress states at the crack initiation regions, ranging from shear-dominated (low stress triaxiality, $\eta \approx 0$) to high triaxiality ($\eta > 0.5$). This approach enabled a systematic correlation between stress-state parameters (stress triaxiality and Lode angle parameter) and microstructural damage mechanisms.

The SH specimen, characterized by near-zero stress triaxiality and Lode angle, exhibited fracture initiation at a critical location marked by the red dashed area in Fig. 6(a). In general, the fracture surface was dominated by a central shear zone, indicative of intense plastic deformation aligned with the shear stress component (Fig. 6(a)). High-magnification SEM images near the initiation site (Fig. 6(a1, a2)) showed a mixed-mode failure mechanism: elongated dimples, characteristic of ductile void coalescence, interspersed with shear fracture, narrow regions of severe localized plasticity, which is different from Fig. 6(a3) showing a typical shear mechanism.

In contrast to the SH specimens, the CH geometry induced a near-uniaxial tensile stress state ($\eta \approx 0.33$), promoting necking at the fracture initiation site (Fig. 6(b), red dashed area). Fractography at the necking region (Fig. 6(b1, b2)) revealed a primary ductile fracture mechanism, evidenced by uniform dimples (2–5 μm diameter) and microvoid coalescence. However, secondary quasi-cleavage facets emerged near macroscopic cracks (Fig. 6(b3)). This transition from ductile to quasi-cleavage fracture (Fig. 6(b4, b5)) at the fracture surface center underscores the role of stress redistribu-

tion: initial plasticity-dominated failure transitions to cleavage as triaxiality increases during post-necking.

The NDB-R6 specimen, designed for moderate triaxiality ($\eta \approx 0.5$), exhibited a large spatial variation in fracture morphology. The fracture surface can be categorized into two distinct zones (Fig. 6(c)): the outer region (outside the white dashed line) dominated by dimples (upper region above the blue dashed line in Fig. 6(c1, c2), and the entire region in Fig. 6(c4)) and the inner region (within the white dashed line) featured a quasi-cleavage fracture with dispersed dimple bands (lower region below the blue dashed line in Fig. 6(c1, c2), and the entire region in Fig. 6(c3, c5)). This gradient reflects the stress triaxiality distribution across the notch [51], with higher values at the center, indicated as the crack initiation area by the red dashed lines, due to constraint effects approaching the plane-strain tension condition.

The NDB-R2 specimen, subjected to the highest triaxiality ($\eta > 0.5$), displayed minimal necking and a highly wavy fracture surface (Fig. 6(d)). Very different from the other specimens, high-magnification analysis revealed for this case a fracture sequence progressing from cleavage initiation (right side indicated by the red dashed lines of Fig. 6(d)) to ductile propagation (left side of Fig. 6(d)):

- (1) Initiation zone (Fig. 6(d1)): typical transgranular cleavage fracture with clear cleavage facets, different from the quasi-cleavage fracture pattern in the NDB-R6 specimen. There are almost no or very minimal microvoids connecting the cleavage fracture planes.
- (2) Transition zone (Fig. 6(d2–d4)): a mixed mode of shallow dimples and quasi-cleavage facets, suggesting ductile tearing as crack-front stresses relaxed.
- (3) Propagation zone (Fig. 6(d5)): a complete ductile fracture region with large and deep dimples without dispersed cleavage fracture facets.

This spatial evolution implies that crack initiation under high triaxiality is governed by cleavage fracture, while subsequent propagation activates ductile mechanisms as the stress triaxiality relaxes.

Fig. 6. Macroscopic damage and fracture behavior analysis of Q&P 1000 steel: SEM fractography of SH (a), CH (b), NDB-R6 (c), and NDB-R2 (d). Details of the fracture process at higher magnification are shown for marked locations.

3.3. Microstructure-level damage mechanism analysis

The fracture surface can reveal the morphology of the fracture and the mode of crack initiation, yet it cannot provide information about the micromechanisms of damage and crack initiation, particularly related to the microstructure features. Therefore, microscopic characterization studies were carried out at the cross-sections of the fractured specimens.

As revealed in Fig. 7, two types of defect generation occur: phase debonding and microcrack initiation, indicated with orange circles and blue rhomboids, respectively. The phase boundary debonding is the main defect type for SH and CH. RA is one key element to phase interface debonding under loading. During the stretching process, the interaction between RA and TMB can exacerbate phase boundary debonding due to stress conditions, as seen in the rightmost detailed images 1, 2, and 4 of Fig. 7, where RA islands contribute significantly to the formation of voids. With the increase of stress triaxiality, the extent of phase boundary debonding of CH is slightly greater. During small deformation, several adjacent phase boundary debonding voids are formed along the TMB/ferrite boundary, as shown in detailed image 3 of Fig. 7. In images 5 and 6, blocky M/A (martensite and/or retained austenite) regions are detaching from the ferrite matrix under applied stress, which also triggers void nucleation.

Another fracture mechanism that can be seen is microcracking, highlighted in blue rhomboids. They can originate inside the M/A and further extend along the grain boundaries. Since both martensite and retained austenite are hard and brittle phases, they tend to crack under stress. This phenomenon is obvious in images 7, 8, and 11 of Fig. 7, where blocky M/A cracking is observed, particularly at higher triaxial stress levels in the NDB-R10 and NDB-R6 regions. As the triaxiality increases, more M/A cracks start to form, propagating through the material and contributing to overall failure.

Additionally, image 12 represents TMB microcracking, which occurs under high triaxiality conditions, leading to cleavage fracture. These observations indicate that as stress triaxiality increases, the failure mode gradually transfers from a void-dominated mode to a cleavage-fracture-dominated one, which is caused by the mechanism shift from phase boundary debonding to mixed cleavage cracking.

4. Discussion

4.1. Effect of stress triaxiality on failure modes

The fracture surfaces of Q&P 1000 steel, analyzed via fractography, reveal a clear dependency of failure modes on stress state, in particular stress triaxiality. Fig. 8 illustrates this transition across specimens subjected to shear (SH, $\eta \approx 0$), uniaxial tension (CH, $\eta \approx 0.33$), and plane-strain tension (NDB-R6, $\eta \approx 0.5$; NDB-R2, $\eta > 0.5$) loading.

- (1) In the low triaxiality region (SH), the fracture surface is dominated by shear lips with localized dimples near the edges. The shear morphology, elongated parallel to the shear direction, is a result of the limited void growth due to suppressed hydrostatic stress, aligning with prior observations in many different steels under shear [20,51–53].
- (2) In the moderate triaxiality region (CH, SDB), the steel exhibits a ductile failure characterized by significant plastic deformation and void coalescence. The fracture surface in this case is populated by deep equiaxed dimples, indicating void growth and coalescence as the dominant mechanism [35,51,54]. These voids are associated mainly with the debonding of phase boundaries and the separation of

Fig. 7. Stress state effects analysis of SEM micrographs of the cross-section of the fractured specimens. (a) SH; (b) CH; (c) NDB-R10; (d) NDB-R6; (e) NDB-R2. Insets 1–14 are zoomed regions. Phase boundary debonding and cracking are indicated with yellow circles and blue rhomboids, respectively.

second-phase constituents in the microstructure (discussed further below).

- (3) In the high triaxiality region (NDB-R6, NDB-R2), the failure mode shifts from a void-dominant mode toward a cleavage fracture pattern. The fracture surface becomes flatter and exhibits features like river-patterned facets, with fewer obvious dimples [52,55,56]. Some regions appear as interlinked planar facets, indicating cleavage fracture along martensitic interfaces (discussed further below).

A schematic representation is given in Fig. 9 to sum up the failure modes of Q&P 1000 under variable loading conditions. The shear mode is represented with green lines, and the quasi-cleavage dominant mode is represented with blue lines, while red lines in-

dicate cleavage fracture, and the dimple fracture is described by orange voids. It is well established that stress triaxiality has a profound influence on metal failure modes. Increasing triaxiality generally promotes void nucleation and growth, leading to classic ductile fracture, whereas lowering the triaxiality shifts the mechanism toward shear-dominated fracture [35,42,54,57]. This trend is rather universal to most ductile metals; however, it is challenged in this study for the 3rd generation AHSS, Q&P steels. In the Q&P steel, it is specifically observed that increasing the stress triaxiality (to a plane-strain tension or higher region) led to a transition from a ductile void-dominated fracture to a quasi-cleavage or cleavage fracture mode.

It is not surprising that the high-strength Q&P steels exhibit brittle-like behavior at rather high stress triaxiality regions [5,25].

Fig. 8. Failure modes of Q&P 1000—SEM fractography of fractured specimens under various stress states.

Fig. 9. Schematic illustration of the failure modes of Q&P 1000 steel under variable stress states. The green lines represent shear fracture mode; the orange circles represent dimple fracture mode; the blue line represents the quasi-cleavage fracture mode, and the red lines represent cleavage fracture.

For example, Xiong et al. [5] noted that intergranular brittle fracture emerged in pre-cracked notched specimens and attributed it to the higher hydrostatic stress promoting rapid austenite-to-martensite transformation at crack tips. This transformation produced a contiguous brittle martensite “necklace” along prior-austenite grain boundaries, facilitating intergranular fracture. However, it is new to discover that rather than intergranular fracture triggered at quite high stress triaxiality region, transgranular (cleavage) fracture can also be present in Q&P steels under medium-high stress triaxiality conditions. As plane-strain tension is a common stress state in many metal forming operations, such as bending, deep drawing, hole expansion, etc., this particular fracture mode transition from dimple dominant to cleavage fracture domi-

nant case presents crucial insights for failure prediction or prevention in forming processes of Q&P steels, in addition to component applications made from Q&P steels.

4.2. Void nucleation and crack initiation mechanisms at various stress states

The potential failure mechanism of the process from shear mode to cleavage fracture mode is summarized and analyzed, as shown in Fig. 10(a). It can be seen that there are two main defects: (1) phase boundary debonding and (2) martensite/austenite cracking. The rhomboids in color represent different cracks, and the red circles represent phase interface debonding. In Fig. 10(b), the defects are categorized into six distinct types (3)–(6), each playing a crucial role in damage evolution under different stress conditions:

- (1) Phase debonding of blocky M/A adjacent to TMB: The RA, especially in its blocky morphology, can undergo rapid strain-induced transformation to martensite. This transformation is often accompanied by localized stress concentrations at the interface between the γ -phase and the surrounding TMB. The mismatch in mechanical properties at these interfaces promotes stress concentration, leading to void nucleation and propagation of cracks along these phase boundaries, ultimately accelerating failure.
- (2) Phase boundary debonding of blocky M/A from ferrite matrix: Due to the lower stability of M/A islands under applied stress, they are more susceptible to premature transformation and decohesion from the ferrite matrix. The stress concentration at the tip of these blocky M/A islands facilitates detachment from adjacent ductile ferrite, initiating void formation, which can often be observed in the TRIP steels [58].
- (3) Ferrite and TMB boundary debonding: At the ferrite-tempered martensite interfaces, voids are typically present due to stress/strain incompatibility under plastic deformation, which is a typical void initiation mechanism in DP steels [59,60]. These voids appear as small discontinuities

Fig. 10. Schematic illustration of microstructure-level damage mechanism (a), defect types (b), and defect counts (c) of Q&P 1000 in a variable stress triaxiality regime. The rhomboids in color represent different cracks, and the red circles represent phases of interface debonding. Microstructural EBSD analysis of voids and cracks: FSD images (d1), orientation maps (d2), band contrast maps (d3), and phase distributions (d4) highlighting fracture mechanisms in Q&P steel.

distributed along the boundary. With increasing applied stress, these voids coalesce, forming an interconnected damage network that results in failure.

- (4) FM cracking: These cracks originate within the FM, which has high yield strength and may undergo cleavage fracture upon exceeding a critical stress level. This is also commonly observed in DP steels and is simply caused by the presence of high dislocation density in FM [61,62].
- (5) Blocky M/A cracking: While RA generally enhances ductility via the TRIP effect, blocky RA regions are particularly vulnerable to cracking under high stress conditions due to the phase transformation to FM, which is sensitive to cleavage fracture.
- (6) TMB cracking: Unlike FM, TM has undergone partitioning and exhibits greater toughness. However, under extreme stress triaxiality conditions, cleavage fracture may still form within the TMB matrix when a critical maximum principal stress is reached.

To quantify the distribution of defects under different stress conditions, Fig. 10(c) presents a statistical analysis of defect counts for specimens tested at varying stress triaxialities. At low and medium triaxiality levels (e.g., SH and CH specimens), phase boundary debonding is the dominant damage mechanism, with limited crack initiation in M/A, fresh, or tempered martensite.

However, as stress triaxiality increases, the defect density rises substantially, and cracks begin to dominate the failure process. The NDB-R2 specimen, which experiences the highest stress triaxiality, exhibits the greatest number of both phase boundary debonding events and cracks. TMB cracks are exclusively observed in this specimen, confirming that TM resists fracture under low and moderate stress triaxiality conditions but suffers from high triaxiality loading. It is noted that although the number count of microcracks in NDB-R2 is less than that of phase boundary debonding, the damage degradation by the cleavage microcracks is dominating and severe, as the effective crack length of microcracks is much longer. Moreover, cracks in the NDB-R2 specimen propagate rapidly upon nucleation, leading to failure at a lower applied stress level without significant prior stress localization, as shown in Fig. 6(d). The substantial number of crack initiations and rapid crack growth explain why the fracture mode in NDB-R2 transitions to cleavage despite the steel's overall high ductility.

Fig. 10(d1–d4) presents an in-depth microstructural examination of fracture mechanisms in Q&P 1000 steel using a combination of forescatter detector (FSD) images, EBSD orientation maps, band contrast maps, and phase distribution maps. This approach aims to investigate the initiation and evolution of damage at the microstructural level in further detail. The upper row of Fig. 10(d1–d4) focuses on void nucleation mechanisms. It further reveals that voids predominantly form at regions exhibiting significant mi-

Fig. 11. Conceptual illustration of fracture mechanism transitions in Q&P 1000 steel under varying stress triaxiality. Specific description of the concept can be found for a pipeline steel deformed at $-196\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [52,63] and titanium alloys [64].

microstructural heterogeneity, as indicated by the band contrast map, and at phase boundaries between distinct microstructural constituents. Specifically, the FM/RA interfaces appear to be critical sites for early void nucleation. As deformation progresses, RA undergoes strain-induced martensitic transformation, which locally generates volumetric expansion and promotes stress concentration at phase boundaries. The newly formed martensite is harder and less ductile than the surrounding tempered martensite and ferrite matrix, leading to a mechanical mismatch that fosters void initiation.

The second row of Fig. 10(d1–d4) highlights cleavage fracture mechanisms, particularly focusing on cracks that originate within TMB regions. The EBSD analysis revealed that cracks propagate preferentially along the (100) crystallographic planes of the TMB grains, the classic cleavage planes for BCC structures. Such cleavage behavior is typically associated with brittle fracture mechanisms, where atomic bonds are broken along specific crystallographic planes under tensile stress with minimal plastic deformation [55]. This cleavage fracture mode implies that, despite the tempered nature of the TMB matrix, it can still fail in a cleavage manner under sufficient local stress concentration, particularly when aligned crystallographic planes coincide with the maximum principal stress direction.

4.3. The mechanics-based root for cleavage fracture at high stress triaxialities

The appearance of cleavage fracture in Q&P 1000 steel under high stress triaxiality conditions, as observed in the NDB-R6/R2 specimens, indicates a fundamental shift in the governing failure mechanism, from strain-governed fracture to stress-controlled fracture. This transition is rooted in fracture mechanics principles and can be rigorously described using a combination of stress- and strain-based fracture criteria. In our previous studies by Shen et al. [52], a detailed derivation of the interaction of the two mechanisms was presented. A brief summary of the main equations is shown below in the context for the current Q&P steel. The mechanism of ductile fracture can be correlated to void nucleation, growth, and coalescence, and therefore is highly dependent on stress triaxiality. A strain-based criterion can be used to express the dependency as demonstrated schematically in Fig. 11. A monotonic dependence of the void-based fracture strain on stress triaxiality is evident when the Lode angle is considered to be a constant. On the other hand, cleavage fracture is commonly understood to be controlled by the maximum principal stress, σ_1 . Cleavage initiates when σ_1 reaches a critical cleavage stress, σ_c , along a crystallographically preferred

plane. This failure occurs with minimal or no plastic deformation and is highly sensitive to the local stress state and microstructural orientation. The condition for cleavage initiation can thus be written as:

$$\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_c \quad (1)$$

While cleavage fracture is fundamentally stress-controlled, it is beneficial in the current study to express fracture in terms of strain criteria, especially for comparison with void-based failure mechanisms. This transformation requires linking the stress-based cleavage criterion to the equivalent plastic strain using the stress–strain relationship of the material [52]. Assuming the hardening behavior of materials follows the Swift law:

$$\bar{\sigma} = A \cdot (\bar{\varepsilon}^p + \bar{\varepsilon}_0^p)^n \quad (2)$$

where $\bar{\sigma}$ and $\bar{\varepsilon}^p$ are the equivalent stress and strain, respectively; A is the strength coefficient, $\bar{\varepsilon}_0^p$ is the initial strain, and n is the strain hardening exponent. By incorporating the hydrostatic stress state via stress triaxiality (η) and the Lode angle parameter ($\bar{\theta}$), the maximum principal stress can be expressed as a function of the equivalent stress, as shown below [65]:

$$\sigma_1 = \left\{ \eta + \frac{2}{3} \cos \left[\frac{\pi}{6} (1 - \bar{\theta}) \right] \right\} \bar{\sigma} \quad (3)$$

Letting $\sigma_1 = \sigma_c$, the stress-based cleavage criterion can be converted into a strain-based one by introducing the Swift hardening law into Eq. (3). This results in a relation of the form:

$$\bar{\varepsilon}_{\sigma_1=\sigma_c} = \left(\frac{\sigma_c}{A \left\{ \eta + \frac{2}{3} \cos \left[\frac{\pi}{6} (1 - \bar{\theta}) \right] \right\}} \right)^{1/n} - \bar{\varepsilon}_0^p \quad (4)$$

This expression can be easily integrated into the same plot as the void-based fracture criterion when keeping the Lode angle constant, as in Fig. 11. It is evident that the cleavage strain to fracture decreases with increasing stress triaxiality, and materials with higher cleavage fracture stress or lower hardening exponent will have a higher critical strain for cleavage, making brittle fracture less likely.

A key concept that emerges from this formulation is the existence of a critical stress triaxiality, η_t , which serves as a threshold between void-based and cleavage-dominated fractures. Below η_t , the local stress is insufficient to trigger cleavage before void-based damage accumulates. Above this threshold, cleavage fracture becomes energetically favorable and can precede void-based mechanisms. The critical triaxiality is material-dependent and governed by the interplay between σ_c and the hardening parameter n . Thus, materials with high cleavage fracture stress (stronger microstructures) or weaker strain hardening behavior (lower n) will exhibit a higher η_t , requiring more severe constraints to initiate cleavage fracture. In contrast, if the cleavage fracture stress is low and the material exhibits strong strain hardening, η_t will be reduced, allowing cleavage to occur under less severe stress states.

In the context of the Q&P 1000 steel studied here, several observations explain the occurrence of cleavage fracture at elevated stress triaxialities. Despite its tempered nature, the martensite phase in Q&P 1000 can still retain high internal residual stresses and inherent crystallographic brittleness. The presence of carbon segregation, dislocation structures, and possible embrittlement effects (e.g., via Mn partitioning or retained carbides) may lower σ_c compared to ideally tough martensite. EBSD analyses in Section 4.2 revealed frequent transgranular cracking along (100) planes in TM, supporting the presence of a relatively low cleavage resistance. On the other hand, Q&P steels typically exhibit a

Fig. 12. Classification of ductile and brittle fracture and their conventional mechanisms in comparison with the new mechanisms.

substantial strain hardening rate due to their multiphase configuration and the transformation of retained austenite. The high hardening exponent increases the flow stress rapidly with strain, contributing to the early accumulation of high σ_1 with stress concentration. This, in turn, lowers the effective η_t , making cleavage initiation feasible at moderate triaxialities. Finally, in the NDB-R6/R2 samples, the crack initiation points experience very high triaxiality, well within the range to activate cleavage fracture based on the material's cleavage fracture stress and hardening response. The resulting stress concentration satisfies the σ_1 criterion for cleavage before void mechanisms can evolve sufficiently.

These factors combine to create a material and stress environment conducive to cleavage fracture, even in steel that is nominally classified as ductile and tough under uniaxial or lower triaxiality conditions. However, one shall not classify the cleavage fracture in NDB-R6/R2 as a brittle fracture, as it is still a ductile fracture with a significant amount of plastic deformation (more discussion in the next section). This mechanistic understanding highlights why Q&P 1000 exhibits a transition in fracture mode under increasing constraint. For applications involving high triaxiality, the primary optimization strategy for Q&P steels should focus on mitigating the cleavage fracture of the tempered martensite phase. The processing of austenite must not only focus on controlling the formation of blocky retained austenite but also on reducing carbon concentration to decrease the brittleness of tempered martensite and improve fracture toughness. Conversely, for low triaxiality applications, such as improving the hole expansion ratio (HER) value, reducing stress or strain inhomogeneity emerges as a critical factor for enhancing local formability. This is evident in samples like the CH specimens, where void growth remains the dominant failure mechanism. For the forming processes of Q&P steels, it is essen-

tial to design operations and component geometries that minimize local triaxialities exceeding the threshold to avoid premature cleavage failure.

4.4. Ductile fracture and brittle fracture distinction

Traditionally, the distinction between ductile and brittle fracture in metallic materials has been made based on the extent of macroscopic plastic deformation prior to failure [55,58]. As illustrated by the dashed black line in Fig. 12, this framework categorizes fractures occurring above the line as ductile, characterized by dimpled or shear fracture mechanisms. In contrast, fractures observed below the line are considered brittle, represented by cleavage or intergranular morphologies, i.e., transgranular propagation through crystallographic planes or interfacial debonding between grains, respectively. While this deformation-based classification has been widely used due to its simplicity and empirical relevance in many conventional metals and alloys, its applicability becomes increasingly limited when applied to AHSS such as Q&P steels. These materials exhibit complex multiphase microstructures and engineered hardening behavior that allow for significant plastic deformation even in the presence of cleavage fracture features, challenging the conventional ductile-brittle definition.

In the current study on Q&P 1000 steel, fractographic analysis via SEM and EBSD investigation reveals that cleavage-like fracture morphologies can coexist with clear evidence of plastic deformation, particularly under high stress triaxiality conditions. This phenomenon suggests that plastic deformation is not sufficient to exclude the occurrence of cleavage fracture in modern high-strength steels. As discussed in the previous section, these observations also point to the need for an additional stress-based fracture

criterion for more accurate prediction of ductile fracture behavior at room temperature, particularly in the new-generation high-strength steels. In addition to the cleavage fracture surfaces in Q&P 1000 steel, particularly discovered in the current study, literature also revealed cases of grain boundary separation, or intergranular fracture, for Q&P steels [5,25]. Despite the intergranular morphology, these cracks also form in specimens that exhibit substantial plastic deformation prior to failure.

This reinforces the conclusion that the failure mechanism of ductile fracture is not simply related to dimple or shear mechanisms, but is much broader, as indicated in Fig. 12, including also cleavage and intergranular fracture, which are often exclusively considered for brittle fracture. Similarly, another conclusion also holds that fracture morphology alone shall not be the only indicator of ductile-brittle distinction, especially when evaluated in isolation from stress-state and microstructural context. The critical insight from this study is that the presence of cleavage or intergranular fracture features should not be automatically interpreted as indicative of brittle fracture in the classical sense of negligible plasticity, and more critically, both cleavage and transgranular fractures should also be expected for the conventionally defined ductile materials. The latter has particular significance for engineering in material forming, material design, and final products.

5. Conclusions

This study systematically investigated the fracture behavior of Q&P 1000 steel under a wide spectrum of stress states by combining mechanical testing, microstructural characterization, and micromechanics-based analysis. The key conclusions are summarized below:

- (1) A clear and progressive transition from void-based (shear and dimple) to cleavage-dominated fracture modes was observed with increasing stress triaxiality. While shear and uniaxial tension promoted classic ductile failure via void distortion or nucleation, growth, and coalescence, higher triaxiality conditions, particularly near plane-strain tension, induced transgranular cleavage fracture even in specimens with substantial global plastic deformation.
- (2) For the first time, this study reports massive transgranular cleavage fracture within tempered martensite in Q&P steels, contrasting with earlier observations in the literature that largely focused on intergranular failure. This finding suggests that cleavage fracture can occur independently of the classical brittle appearance and becomes a damage mechanism for the ductile fracture mode.
- (3) Zooming into the micromechanisms of failure, two primary defects were identified: phase boundary debonding and martensite/austenite cracks, with an increasing trend towards higher stress triaxialities. It is revealed that damage initiates preferentially at boundaries involving retained austenite (RA), fresh martensite (FM), and tempered martensite/bainite (TMB). Void nucleation was commonly found at high-strain phase boundaries, while cleavage cracks tended to propagate along (100) cleavage planes within tempered martensite grains under elevated triaxiality. Six dominant defect types were identified and mapped to specific microstructural configurations.
- (4) A practical and reproducible approach for distinguishing fresh and tempered martensite, ferrite, retained austenite, and bainite in Q&P 1000 was proposed based on EBSD data and MTEX post-processing. This strategy can assist correlation between microstructural constituents and fracture-initiating features, thereby providing a reliable methodolog-

ical tool for future studies on complex multiphase and Q&P steels.

- (5) A mechanics-based understanding of the transition from void-based to cleavage and intergranular fracture was established, linking cleavage-like initiation to the attainment of a critical maximum principal stress. A material-specific critical stress triaxiality threshold was identified, beyond which cleavage or intergranular fracture dominates. In Q&P 1000 steel, this threshold is reduced by low cleavage fracture stress in tempered martensite and a high strain hardening exponent, which is beneficial for ductility and global formability but increases the cleavage fracture susceptibility.
- (6) These insights provide a deeper understanding of failure mechanisms in Q&P steels and offer practical guidance for improving fracture resistance. For applications involving high triaxiality, design strategies should target the reduction of carbon-induced brittleness in tempered martensite and suppression of blocky retained austenite. For forming operations involving low to moderate triaxiality, enhancing phase compatibility and reducing stress localization are essential for delaying damage initiation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Rongfei Juan: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Junhe Lian:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Acknowledgment

The authors acknowledge the funding from the European Union's Research Fund for Coal and Steel program under grant agreement No. 101112540 (Sup3rForm).

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